

Towards UAM introduction - Social and Environmental Performance Indicators

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Urban Air Mobility (UAM), as a new transportation system, offers the potential for greener and faster mobility of passengers and cargo, in and around urban environments. UAM is designed to improve the current system, by using the airspace above congested urban areas thus reducing pressure and reliance on ground-based infrastructure. Although the potential social benefits of UAM are indisputable, the success of UAM introduction and wide use will strongly depend on the confidence and acceptance of the citizens and future UAM users. Impact on overall quality of life, as a multidimensional concept that encompasses physical health, mental and emotional well-being, social relationships, economic status, education, and the environment, becomes a significant issue.

The European Union Aviation Safety Agency (EASA) study, conducted on the societal acceptance of UAM operations, showed EU citizens generally positive attitude towards UAM. However, citizens indicated that they want to limit their exposure to safety, noise, security and environmental impact. The survey results also showed that user diversity strongly influences both acceptance and perceived interruptions.

This research is a part of the SESAR MUSE (Measuring U-Space Social and Environmental Impact) project. The aim of this research is to define a set of performance indicators (PIs), able to capture the full range of UAM's impacts on citizens' quality of life.

Conducted comprehensive literature review in the field revealed that current U-space performance frameworks include different indicators to evaluate UAM's social and environmental impact. Literature indisputably indicates areas of the highest concern, like noise, visual pollution and privacy concerns. Nevertheless, to this date, indicators are mainly too generic and aggregated to properly capture the broad variety of impacts of UAM operations.

To define the Social and Environmental Framework, firstly main issues (focus areas) are identified. Apart from noise, visual pollution and privacy concerns, some other aspects are also observed, such as access and equity, economic aspects, emissions, etc. In the next step, one of the specific objectives of the MUSE project is addressed, which is to develop PIs with the highest possible level of geographical, temporal, demographic, socioeconomic and behavioural resolution. Proposed PIs (38 in total), defined in a way that enables the analysis of the interaction between UAM impacts and factors such as age, gender, place of residence, level of income, occupational status, etc. (called cross-cutting areas), is the main contribution of this research. In this paper, we present the approach for defining focus areas, cross/cutting areas, proposed indicators and their measuring mechanisms.

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